

ECONOMIC GROWTH AND FERTILITY TRANSITION IN INDIA: EVIDENCE FROM THE POST-LIBERALISATION PERIOD

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Abstract: Unified growth theory predicts that, to escape the Malthusian regime of stagnation and achieve sustained economic growth, the fertility rate falls over time. India, an emerging economy with the world's largest population, has also witnessed a steady decline in its fertility rate over the last few decades. However, there remains a significant research gap in studying how economic growth has affected the fertility decline in India. This study aims to examine how economic growth in the post-liberalisation period has contributed to the decline in fertility. Using time series data from 1991 to 2022, we find that economic growth, indicated by per capita income, inversely affects India's fertility rate. Furthermore, we find that female labour force participation and female education also have an inverse effect on fertility, whereas infant mortality rate directly affects fertility. Based on the findings of this study, we provide important policy insights to address the challenge of declining fertility in India.

Keywords: Fertility decline, Total fertility rate, Unified growth theory, Fertility determinants, Time-series econometrics.

1. Introduction

In the process of demographic transition in a developing country, the fertility trend follows a common transition path. Generally, it is observed that the fertility rate transits from a high rate to a low rate. Which variable determines this fertility transition is a matter of interest for researchers. Although several robust determinants of fertility transition—such as female labour force participation rate, female education, contraceptive prevalence, and infant mortality transition—have already been identified, the most important and widely discussed topic remains how economic growth affects the fertility rate. Malthus (1798) wrote that any rise in income causes an increase in the total fertility rate (TFR). However, this direct effect of income on TFR was later criticised, as empirical studies

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found an inverse relationship between income and TFR (Balan, 2015). This effect suggests that a rise in income leads to a decline in TFR, causing fertility to transit from a high level to a low level in the process of economic growth.² According to Galor (2005), a negative effect of income on fertility is expected in a modern economy. Galor (2005) noted that when an economy is in the Malthusian epoch of stagnation, any rise in income leads to an increase in TFR. However, when an economy transits from the Malthusian epoch to a sustained economic growth regime, a negative effect of income on fertility emerges. This negative effect occurs because the ‘quality’ of children becomes more important for parents than the ‘quantity’ of children (Becker and Lewis, 1973). Furthermore, economic growth brings several structural shifts, not only in the economy but also in social structures, cultural values, and medical advancements. Therefore, a negative effect of rising income on fertility is often observed.

In the existing literature, several prior studies aim to determine how economic growth affects the fertility transition of countries. Such studies are available in both single-country time series data and multi-country panel data. For example, Narayan and Peng (2006) used time series data from China and found that economic growth affects fertility inversely. Herzer et al. (2012) used panel data from 20 countries globally and found that per capita GDP negatively affects the fertility rate. Many more studies in the academic literature examine the effect of economic growth on fertility rate (Tang and Tey, 2018; Subramaniam et al., 2018). However, such investigation based studies on the Indian economy is rare, presenting an important research gap that this study aims to address.

To examine how economic growth affects the fertility rate in India, we exclusively focus on the post-liberalisation period. There are two main reasons for this choice. The primary reason is the significant rise in India’s growth rate during the post-liberalisation period (see Figure 1). While from 1960 to 1990, per capita income (PCI) increased by 72 per cent, India’s PCI rose by 292 per cent during 1991-2022. Furthermore, during the same period, a sharp decline in the TFR was also observed in India. Previous studies have explored how post-liberalisation transitions in various macroeconomic, developmental, and health parameters have occurred (Simon-Kumar, 2007; Barik et al., 2022). However, less attention has been given to fertility transition during this period. Thus, this study examines the research question as to how post-liberalisation economic growth affects the fertility rate in India.

The secondary reason for selecting the post-liberalisation period is to ensure the robustness of our results. To establish a robust relationship between economic growth and fertility transition, we conduct a robustness test by incorporating additional control variables, following the specification of Narayan and Peng (2006). In Section 2.2 of this study, we discuss the additional control variables in detail and explain that we estimate the long-run cointegrating regression using three such control variables. Among them, female labour force participation rate serves as a major control variable, for which data are available only from 1990. Hence, we restrict our analysis to the post-liberalisation period.

Regarding the contribution and relevance of the research question, this study makes multiple contributions to both academic literature and policy discussions. In terms of academic contributions, first, it fills an important research gap in the Indian context. Although existing studies have explored the impact of economic growth on fertility transition in various countries, similar research on the Indian economy remains scarce. This study aims to bridge the gap. Second, it contributes to the literature on the demographic-economic paradox by providing empirical evidence from India.

² This negative relationship is known as the demographic-economic paradox in academic literature (Balan, 2015).

From a policy perspective, firstly, India's fertility rate is declining rapidly and has recently fallen below the replacement level of TFR. Global experience indicates that once fertility reaches critically low levels, reversing the trend through policy incentives becomes a daunting task (Lutz et al., 2006). Understanding the role of economic growth in fertility transition is crucial in this context, as it helps determine whether sustained economic expansion is a key driver of India's fertility decline. Such an understanding enables policymakers to anticipate future demographic shifts and design timely interventions to prevent excessively low fertility, which could otherwise lead to adverse economic and social consequences. Secondly, since 1991 (the beginning of the Indian economy has experienced sustained economic growth, which is expected to continue in the future. By focusing on the post-liberalisation period, this study provides more recent findings for policy discussions in the Indian context. Moreover, we use additional control variables such as female education, female labour force participation, and infant mortality rate (see Section 2.2). These additional variables in the post-liberalisation period show significant changes. By exploring their influence on fertility transition, this study highlights the broader macro-level or distal determinants of fertility rate.

To summarise, this study provides a holistic understanding of post-liberalisation fertility dynamics in India and examines how economic growth, along with additional distal determinants, has shaped the country's fertility transition. This is important for both academic inquiry and policy formulation.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. In Section 2, we discuss the methodology adopted for this research and the data sources used. In Section 3, we present the results of our main model and interpret the results. Finally, in Section 4, we conclude with a summary of our study.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Data

Secondary-level time series data is utilised in this study. The time frame of the analysis is restricted to the period from 1991 to 2022. As discussed earlier, this time frame has been chosen for two reasons. Firstly, our core objective is to analyse how post-liberalisation economic growth affected India's fertility rate, as the country has witnessed a significant decline in fertility over the last few decades. Secondly, for control variables such as female labour force participation rate (FLFPR), data is available only since 1991.

We use the World Development Indicators database to collect the data. Total fertility rate (TFR) is used to represent fertility trend, while GDP per capita serves as an indicator of PCI, which is widely recognised as a standard measure of economic growth in the growth economics literature. Female gross enrolment in secondary education acts as a proxy variable for female education (EDU). Additionally, infant mortality rate (IMR) and female labour force participation rate (FLFPR) is included as other important control variables. Based on these variables, sourced from the World Development Indicators, the econometric models are estimated in this study.

2.2. Methodology

In this study, we show the long-run effect of economic growth on fertility transition in India. To demonstrate the long-run relationship, we first check whether there is a long-run stable relationship, known as cointegration, between these two variables. For the purpose of testing cointegration, we use a combined cointegration test. The combined cointegration test provided by Bayer and Hanck (2012), also known as the Bayer Hanck (BH) cointegration test, is employed in our analysis. The advantage of the BH cointegration test is that it overcomes the shortcomings of popular

cointegration tests such as Engle and Granger (1987), Johansen (1988), Boswijk (1994), and Banerjee et al. (1998). These existing tests often lack uniformity in results, and the findings are frequently contradictory. The outcomes of these tests heavily depend on the inclusion or exclusion of nuisance parameters, which may not be of primary interest but are included in the model to improve its fit. The BH cointegration test combines these existing tests and provides more reliable and robust cointegration results. The BH test applies the Fisher (1934) formula to combine the p-values of individual tests:

$$EG - J = -2 [\ln(P_{EG}) + (P_J)] \tag{1}$$

$$EG - J - BAN - BO = -2 [\ln(P_{EG}) + (P_J) + \ln(P_{BAN}) + \ln(P_{BO})] \tag{2}$$

In equations (1) and (2), EG, J, BAN and BO stand for the cointegration tests propounded by Engle and Granger (1987), Johansen (1988), Banerjee et al. (1988), and Boswijk (1994), respectively. In BH cointegration test, if the value of the Fisher statistic exceeds the critical value, we conclude the presence of cointegration. In this study, we consider the critical value at the 5 per cent significance level.

Once we confirm the presence of cointegration in the model, we employ cointegrating regression to estimate the long run relationship between the variables. For this purpose, we use the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) method. FMOLS is a specialised form of cointegrating regression developed by Phillips and Hansen (1990). The advantage of using FMOLS lies in its ability to provide unbiased estimates in the presence of non-stationarity in the variables, a condition under which ordinary least squares (OLS) tend to yield biased results. FMOLS is robust to endogeneity bias and serial correlation problems. Therefore, FMOLS produces reliable results when cointegration exists among variables (Khan et al., 2019).

In a cointegrating regression such as FMOLS, a stable long run relationship is assumed between the variables. When cointegration is present, any non-stationary variable that is excluded becomes part of the residual term, making it non-stationary and thereby violating the condition for cointegration (Everaert, 2011). The coefficient estimated in a cointegrating regression is considered super-consistent, and this consistency is maintained even when other control variables are included or excluded (Herzer, 2020). Consequently, in cointegrating regression, the coefficient remains unbiased even in the absence of control variables (Herzer, 2019). This feature of cointegrating regression marks a clear improvement over traditional OLS regression, where the inclusion or exclusion of control variables significantly alters the coefficients. Therefore, in the baseline model of this study, we consider TFR as a function of PCI only and do not include any control variables. However, we do not take the proposition of super-consistency for granted. In the robustness test, we include relevant control variables. Along with PCI, we consider three additional control variables: EDU, FLFPR, and IMR. This specification—in which TFR is modelled as a function of PCI, FSEC, FLFPR, and IMR—is adapted from the seminal work of Narayan and Peng (2006), who identified the determinants of TFR in the case of China. This specification has since been used in several other empirical studies for other countries by various authors, including Narayan and Peng (2006), Tang and Tey (2017), and Subhramaniam et al. (2018). Accordingly, the regression equation of our study can be written as:

$$TFR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PCI_t + u_t \tag{1}$$

$$TFR_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 PCI_t + \gamma_2 FLFPR_t + \gamma_3 EDU_t + \gamma_4 IMR_t + \epsilon_t \tag{2}$$

In equation (1), TFR_t represents TFR at period t . PCI_t represents PCI at period t . β_0 is the intercept term, while β_1 denotes the long-run coefficient. u_t is the residual term.

In equation (2), TFR_t , PCI_t , $FLFPR_t$, EDU_t , and IMR_t represents TFR, PCI, FLFPR, EDU and IMR, respectively—all at period t . γ_0 represents the intercept term, whereas $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_4$ represent the long-run coefficients. ϵ_t denotes the residual term.

To address the issue of scale differences and to facilitate interpretation of the regression results, we apply natural logarithmic transformation to all the variables. Accordingly, equations (1) and (2) are rewritten as:

$$\ln TFR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln PCI_t + u_t \quad (3)$$

$$\ln TFR_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \ln PCI_t + \gamma_2 \ln FLFPR_t + \gamma_3 \ln EDU_t + \gamma_4 \ln IMR_t + \epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Here, it is important to clarify that the objective of our study is to identify the macroeconomic determinants of fertility, which is fundamentally different from the proximate determinants of fertility proposed by Bongaarts (1978). The proximate determinant framework identifies variables that directly affect fertility. These variables include postpartum infecundability, contraceptive use, nuptiality, and induced abortion.

The analysis of proximate determinants is conducted at the individual and biological level, where these determinants operate through biological and behavioural pathways. However, the focus of this paper is on macro-level determinants of fertility rate. Macro-level variables, also known as distal determinants of fertility, are analysed at the societal, economic, and population levels. Changes in distal determinants bring about social, economic, and cultural transformations, which in turn influence individual decision-making related to fertility.

Studying this macro-level determinants of fertility rates is important because it helps to identify the broader socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental factors that shape population dynamics. Understanding these determinants is crucial for policymakers to design effective interventions, such as improving education, healthcare, and economic opportunities, to address fertility-related challenges. Additionally, it provides insights into long-term demographic trends, which are essential for sustainable development and resource planning. Furthermore, as noted earlier, in the case of India, there exists a significant research gap concerning the study of macro-level determinants of fertility, particularly in the post-liberalisation era. Although studies such as Gupta et al. (2014) and Singh et al. (2022) have already explored the proximate determinants of fertility in India, there has been limited focus on macro-level factors.

Hence, this study primarily focuses on the macro-level determinants of fertility in India. The baseline model addresses our core objective by examining how economic growth affects the fertility rate. In the robustness analysis, we extend the model in the line of Narayan and Peng (2006) to identify additional macro-level determinants of fertility.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Long-Run Trend in Fertility Rate in India

Before delving into the econometric analysis and examining the role of economic growth in the decline of fertility in India, this study first discusses the long-run trends in the fertility rate.

In the 1960s, the fertility transition in India began, with the fertility rate starting to fall from a high level to a low level. In the post-liberalisation period, TFR declined further, recently reaching a sub-replacement level, with the TFR in 2022 standing at 2.0. According to Radkar (2020), although from 1951 to 1981 the high TFR led to rapid population growth, from 1981 onwards there were clear signs of a population growth slowdown due to declining fertility rates. However, this downward

trend raises critical questions, most importantly, how far it will continue. Bhattacharjee et al. (2024) predict that if the trend persists, by 2050 India’s TFR could fall as low as 1.29. Such a scenario is highly concerning, as an extremely low TFR not only poses economic challenges but also carries serious societal implications. Global evidence from East Asian and European countries suggests that policymakers must act before fertility rates reach alarmingly low levels (Van Dalen and Henkens, 2021). In this context, this study highlights a major macro-level determinant of fertility, economic growth, and its influence on India’s fertility transition.

As discussed earlier, this study specifically focuses on the post-liberalisation period of fertility transition, as this era is considered the phase of high economic growth in India, when the economy moved from a low growth trajectory to a regime of sustained expansion. In the unified growth literature, it is argued that when a developing economy enters a sustained growth regime, fertility rates inevitably decline (Galor, 2005). This is because if rising income were directed towards increasing fertility, technological progress would be impeded. Thus, the fertility transition literature consistently shows that rising economic growth is associated with falling fertility rates.

As shown in Figure 1, during the post-liberalisation period, India’s TFR displayed a consistent downward trend. Similarly, Figure 2 indicates that the annual growth rate of TFR has been negative in every year, suggesting a consistent decline in fertility. At the same time, Figures 3 and 4 illustrate a steady upward trend in per capita income (PCI), with the only exception being the COVID-19 pandemic, when GDP growth fell for the first time in three decades. From these initial observations, it appears that TFR fell while PCI rose in the same period. However, the extent to which PCI influenced the decline in TFR can only be determined through the robust econometric analysis that follows in the subsequent sections of this study.

Figure 1: Fertility Transition in India during the Post-LPG Period

Source: World Development Indicators.

Figure 2: Percentage Change in fertility during the Post-LPG Period

Figure 3: PCI Transition in India

Source: World Development Indicators.

Figure 4: Annual GDP Growth

3.2. Econometric Analysis

This study runs two models. Based on the idea of Herzer (2020), we do not use any control variables to show the effect of PCI on TFR in the first model. This model relies on the concept of super-consistency of estimation in the presence of cointegration, and we refer to it as the baseline model. In the second model, we include appropriate control variables to check the robustness of the first model. This is the extended model in our study. The second model also provides insights into how other relevant variables play a role in the fertility transition of India.

3.2.1. Unit Root Test

To run the appropriate econometric models, the first step is to check for the presence of a unit root in the model. For this purpose, we use the Perron unit root test with a breakpoint. Breakpoint unit root tests are a more advanced version and an extension of traditional unit root tests. They allow for structural breaks in the time series. Therefore, unit root tests with structural breaks are considered more reliable and less biased than traditional unit root tests (Perron, 1989).

Perron's (1989) unit root testing method, which treats structural breaks as exogenous, is used in this study. In Table 1, we examine the unit root properties of all variables used in this study. Table 1 shows that all the variables are stationary either in level form or after first differencing, and no variable is stationary at the second difference.

It is important to note that in our econometric estimation, we include the logarithmic transformation of all variables. This approach has several advantages. First, it removes scale differences across variables. Second, logarithmic transformations make the results easier to interpret, as they allow for interpretation in percentage terms.

Table 1: Perron Unit Root Test with Breakpoint

Variable	Intercept	Break point	Trend + Intercept	Break point
lnTFR	-2.57	2002	-2.67	2005
Δ lnTFR	-5.72*	2014	-6.24*	2014
lnPCI	-1.40	2003	-3.25	2019
Δ lnPCI	-8.31*	2020	-8.65*	2020
lnFLFPR	-2.86	2010	-3.09	2010
Δ lnFLFPR	-5.76*	2020	-8.81*	2020
lnEDU	-2.92	2000	-3.52	2010
Δ lnEDU	-6.08*	1998	-7.48*	2000
lnIMR	-3.01	2005	-4.90**	2010

Note: * and ** denote rejection of the null hypothesis at the 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Source: The authors

3.2.2. Analysis of the Baseline Model

In Table 1, we observe that both TFR and PCI are non-stationary at level but become stationary at first difference. When the raw data are non-stationary but become stationary after differencing, there is a possibility of cointegration. Cointegration checks whether the linear combination of non-stationary variables exhibits stationary properties. In simpler terms, cointegration indicates the presence of a stable long-run relationship between variables. In this study, we use the BH cointegration test to examine the presence of cointegration, and the results are reported in Table 2.

In Table 2, the Fisher-type test statistics in both the EG-J and EG-J-BAN-BO tests exceed

the critical value at a 5 per cent significance level in the BH cointegration model. Thus, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected, indicating the presence of a cointegrating relationship or a stable long-run association in the model.

Table 2: BH Cointegration Test (Model 1)

Model	Fisher-type test statistics				Cointegration
	EG-J		EG-J-BAN-BO		
TFR=f(PCI)	Test statistics	21.85	Test statistics	23.30	Yes
	Critical value*	11.23	Critical value*	21.93	

Note: * represents the critical value at the 5 per cent significance level.

Source: The authors

Once we confirm the presence of cointegration, the next step is to estimate the coefficient of the relationship. For this purpose, we employ the FMOLS model. Table 3 presents the results of the FMOLS estimation. The p-values in the table indicate that PCI significantly affects TFR. The estimated coefficient suggests that a 1 per cent increase in PCI results in a 0.5 per cent decline in TFR in the post-liberalisation period. Hence, we conclude that economic growth has influenced fertility reduction in India. For a developing country, a decline in fertility alongside a rise in PCI is an essential condition for economic growth. This is because if TFR also increases with rising PCI, the country remains trapped in a Malthusian regime of stagnation and cannot transit into a regime of sustained economic growth (Galor, 2005). Hence, the decline in TFR alongside a rise in PCI is a positive sign for economic growth in India under the lens of the unified growth model. However, such a relationship also raises an important question. The fertility rate in India is falling rapidly compared to other countries. India has already achieved sub-replacement level fertility, but its PCI remains very low. If we compare this scenario with developed nations, we can clearly observe that when those countries first reached sub-replacement fertility levels, their PCI was multiple times higher. Thus, India is becoming older before becoming rich.

A possible explanation for this in the Indian context can be twofold. Firstly, it is plausible that the income elasticity of fertility in India is higher than in other countries. Therefore, even a small rise in PCI is associated with a rapid decline in TFR. Secondly, it is also possible that, beyond economic growth, other factors are influencing the fertility decline in India. A part of this issue is addressed in Section 3.3, where we examine which other variables are affecting the fertility rate in India.

Table 3: FMOLS Model (for Baseline Model)

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
Constant	4.49*	89.96	0.00
lnPCI	-0.50*	-71.03	0.00

Note: * refers to the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 1% significance level.

Source: The authors

3.2.3. Analysis of the Extended Model

The FMOLS model presented in Table 3 serves as our baseline model, based on the claim in the cointegration literature that cointegrating models are free from omitted variable bias (Herzer, 2020). To verify this claim, we apply FMOLS to an extended specification model. This exercise has two key implications. Firstly, it ensures the robustness of our estimations, thereby increasing the reliability

of the study. Secondly, it provides insights into other macro-level determinants of the fertility rate in India.

In Section 2, we have already discussed the extended variables used in this model and the rationale behind their inclusion. Before delving into the econometric model, it is necessary to establish the theoretical linkages of these independent variables.

The first variable included in this model (in addition to PCI) is female education (EDU). Studies have documented a negative effect of EDU on TFR (Jain, 1981; Ali and Gurmu, 2018). Kasarda (1979) provides a theoretical framework explaining the indirect effects of female education on TFR. According to this framework, female education increases the age of marriage and first birth, enhances employment opportunities and socioeconomic mobility, reduces the economic utility of children, increases exposure to mass media, and improves husband-wife communication, all of which contribute to a decline in TFR.

The second variable in our model is the female labour force participation rate (FLFPR). The incompatibility hypothesis in the academic literature predicts an inverse relationship between FLFPR and TFR. This hypothesis suggests that childbearing and employment both require significant time and effort, leading to a trade-off between the two. Studies such as Mishra and Smyth (2010) have previously found an inverse effect of FLFPR on TFR. However, in academic discussions, the societal response hypothesis suggests that a positive effect of FLFPR on TFR may also exist. This hypothesis argues that, over time, societal attitudes towards working mothers evolve, and workplaces become more accommodating. Empirical literature has also documented cases where FLFPR has a positive effect on TFR (Ahn and Mira, 2002).

The final variable included in the extended model is the infant mortality rate (IMR). Palloni and Rafalimanana (1999) identified several theoretical channels through which IMR affects TFR. Firstly, when the probability of child survival is low, parents tend to have more children than their desired family size as a precautionary measure. This phenomenon is known as the insurance or hoarding effect. Secondly, the death of an infant has significant psychological effects on parents, influencing their future fertility decisions. Additionally, infant mortality leads to the early cessation of breastfeeding, which triggers the resumption of ovulation and increases the likelihood of conception, a mechanism referred to as the physiological effect. Furthermore, when IMR is low, the need for replacement children diminishes, leading to a reduction in TFR, a phenomenon known as the replacement effect. These direct relationships between IMR and TFR have been documented in previous studies, including Bongaarts and Hodgson (2022).

Once we know the probable theoretical linkage between these variables and fertility, our next step is to estimate the model. In Table 1, we already observe that all the variables used in this model exhibit stationarity either at the level or at the first difference, and no variable is stationary at the second difference. Given the presence of non-stationary elements, we test for cointegration in the extended model. Table 4 presents the results of the BH cointegration test. The BH cointegration test shows that the EG-J-BAN-BO and EG-J test statistics in the extended model exceed the critical value at the 5 per cent significance level, indicating that the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected. Hence, we conclude that a stable long-run relationship exists among the variables in the extended model.

Table 4: BH Cointegration Test (Model 2)

Model	Fisher-type test statistics				Cointegration
	EG-J		EG-J-BAN-BO		
TFR=f(PCI,FLFPR,EDU,IMR)	Test statistics	28.34	Test statistics	37.35	Yes
	Critical value*	10.57	Critical value*	20.14	

Note: * represents the critical value at the 5 per cent significance level.

Source: The authors.

To estimate the coefficients in the cointegrating regression, we apply FMOLS in the same manner as we did in the baseline model. Table 5 shows the results of the extended model. Similar to the baseline model, we can see that PCI affects TFR inversely. Hence, our results regarding the effect of economic growth on TFR remain robust in the post-reform period. The extended model shows that a 1 per cent rise in PCI causes a 0.32 per cent fall in TFR.

The inverse effect of PCI on TFR (as evident in both models) can be explained through various channels. Firstly, theoretically, according to the ‘New Home Economics’ school of thought, parents derive utility from three factors: the quantity of children, the quality of children, and the consumption of other goods (Becker and Lewis, 1973). As the economy transitions from being primary sector-driven to a modern sector-driven economy, the demand for labour falls while the demand for human capital increases. Thus, fertility rates change endogenously within the economy through the quantity-quality trade-off, as parents prioritise the quality of children over quantity. As a result, fertility rates decline as economic growth progresses.

Furthermore, economic growth not only brings changes to the economy but also transforms societal values regarding traditional gender roles, family institutions, and long-standing cultural norms. These factors also contribute to the reduction of TFR. Moreover, as parents’ PCI rises, the opportunity cost of having children increases, reinforcing the inverse relationship between PCI and TFR. Previous studies, such as Herzer et al. (2012) and Ozbay Das (2020), have also empirically found an inverse effect of economic growth on TFR at the country level. Hence, our study aligns with existing theoretical and empirical knowledge, demonstrating that fertility rates declined in the post-liberalisation period and that economic growth played a pivotal role in this decline.

Our second variable is FLFPR. The findings in Table 6 show that as FLFPR rises by 1 per cent, TFR falls by 0.17 per cent. These findings are consistent with the incompatibility hypothesis, which suggests that mothers’ economic activity reduces the number of children they have. In developing countries like India, the societal response hypothesis is weak, and an inverse relationship between FLFPR and TFR is generally observed. This finding is consistent with other studies at the country level, such as Kim (2014), which also observed a negative effect of FLFPR on TFR.

Our third variable in the extended model is EDU. As discussed earlier, a theoretical inverse effect of EDU on TFR is expected. Table 5 confirms this, showing that EDU affects TFR inversely. Specifically, a 1 per cent rise in EDU causes a 0.20 per cent fall in TFR in India. This finding is consistent with empirical evidence on the impact of education on TFR (Jain, 1981; Ali and Gurmu, 2018). An increase in female education empowers women to make household and reproductive decisions. Furthermore, contraceptive prevalence among educated women is significantly higher (Nyarko, 2015), which, in turn, reduces fertility rates.

Our fourth variable in the extended model, IMR, has a positive effect on TFR. As IMR increases, TFR also increases, and vice versa. Specifically, a 1 per cent rise in IMR causes a 0.11 per

cent rise in TFR. Global evidence suggests that a decline in IMR is generally followed by a decline in TFR. In regions where the probability of child survival is high, the replacement need for children is lower, leading to a decrease in TFR (Palloni and Rafalimanana, 1999).

Table 5: Robustness Test with Control Variables

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
Constant	4.22*	10.26	0.00
lnPCI	-0.32*	-6.37	0.00
lnFLFPR	-0.17**	-2.23	0.03
lnEDU	-0.20*	-3.80	0.00
lnIMR	0.11**	2.16	0.04

Note: * and ** denote rejection of the null hypothesis at the 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Source: The authors

4. Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrated that economic growth in the post-liberalisation period reduced India's TFR. Furthermore, in the extended model, we found that, along with the inverse effect of PCI, female labour force participation and female education also affect TFR negatively, whereas infant mortality rate affects TFR directly. Based on the study's findings, we provided several relevant policy insights to manage India's fertility transition.

Although our study offers valuable insights for both academic literature and policy circles, there are certain limitations that we would like to highlight. Based on these limitations, we also provide suggestions for future research. Firstly, our study utilises aggregate-level time series data. Future studies could account for state-level variations by employing panel data analysis to examine fertility transitions in India more comprehensively. Secondly, we limit our study to the post-liberalisation period, as our primary objective is to assess the impact of post-liberalisation economic growth on fertility transition in India. Additionally, for variables such as FLFPR, a longer time series was not used. Future research could explore fertility dynamics in India over a longer timeframe. Studies should take inspiration from Herzer et al. (2012), who analysed fertility transition over an extended period at the global level. Future studies are highly encouraged in these areas.

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